

Master thesis on Sound and Music Computing
Universitat Pompeu Fabra

Evaluation of Drum Rhythmspace in a Music Production Environment

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Supervisors: Daniel Gómez-Marín, Sergi Jordà

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Contents

1	Introduction	1
2	State of the Art	4
2.0.1	Drum loop analysis, comparison, and generation	4
2.0.2	Music interfaces for music building block retrieval	11
2.0.3	Evaluation of lowD spaces as interfaces	14
3	Methodology: Rhythmspace Plugin Design & Development	17
3.1	Design and Development of the Rhythmspace Plugin	17
3.1.1	Rhythmspace Puredata prototype	18
3.1.2	Rhythmspace VST plugin	20
4	Experiments Evaluating Rhythmspace	24
4.1	Experiment 1: Evaluating Rhythmspace in Music Production	25
4.1.1	Preparation	25
4.1.2	Procedure	26
4.1.3	Evaluation: Rhythmspace in the context of Music production.	28
4.1.4	Results: Rhythmspace in the context of Music production.	30
4.2	Experiment 2: Ranking Drum Sequences	36
4.2.1	Preparation	36
4.2.2	Procedure	37
4.2.3	Evaluating Participant’s Drum Sequences	39
4.2.4	Results: Ranking Drum Sequences	40

5	Conclusions	48
5.1	Discussion	48
5.2	Future Works	50
	List of Figures	52
	List of Tables	54
	Bibliography	55
A	First Appendix	63
A.1	Experiment 1	63
A.1.1	Script	63
A.1.2	Links: Experiment 1	64
A.2	Experiment 2	65
A.2.1	Script	65
A.2.2	Links: Experiment 2	65
B	Second Appendix	66
B.1	Code Links	66

Dedication

This work is dedicated to my mother and sister, who always support me in all of my adventures around the world, the two most important women in my life. Additionally, to all the lovely people I met at MTG, I will forever cherish the relationships I made here.

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Abstract

In modern computer-based music production, vast musical data libraries are essential. However, their presentation via subpar interfaces can hinder creativity, complicating the selection of ideal sequences. While low-dimensional space solutions have been suggested, their evaluations in real-world music production remain limited.

In this study, we focus on Rhythmspace, a two-dimensional platform tailored for the exploration and generation of drum patterns in symbolic MIDI format. Our primary objectives encompass two main aspects: first, the evolution of Rhythmspace into a VST tool specifically designed for music production settings, and second, a thorough evaluation of this tool to ascertain its performance and applicability within the music production scenario.

The tool's development necessitated transitioning the existing Rhythmspace, which operates in Puredata and Python, into a VST compatible with Digital Audio Workstations (DAWs) using the JUCE(C++) framework. Our evaluation encompassed a series of experiments, starting with a composition test where participants crafted drum sequences followed by a listening test, wherein participants ranked the sequences from the initial experiment.

The results show that Rhythmspace and similar tools are beneficial, facilitating the exploration and creation of drum patterns in a user-friendly and intuitive manner, and enhancing the creative process for music producers. These tools not only streamline the drum sequence generation but also offer a fresh perspective, often serving as a source of inspiration in the dynamic realm of electronic music production.

Keywords: Rhythmspace, JUCE framework, Low-dimensional Space Evaluation.

Chapter 1

Introduction

Music creation has long been viewed as a fundamental type of human creativity, profoundly embedded in our cultural identity. The way music is made today has been substantially transformed by technology, with machines and digital systems playing a crucial role in the creative process. Digital music creation tools are widely available, yet they frequently fall short of fostering the inspiration and creative inquiry that are essential to the music-making process. When creating songs, artists and producers of electronic music often heavily rely on massive, carefully selected libraries of data, including audio and symbolic loops, one-shot samples, virtual instruments, and synth presets [1]. These musical blocks thanks to online resources like Freesound [2] or Splice[3] are easily available to artists. Even so, sorting these massive amounts of samples can be a time-consuming process, pointing to a more efficient and user-friendly data representation. Digital audio workstations (DAWs) only offer list-based search tools to assist in organizing media, but they frequently lack easy browsing techniques. As an alternative, third-party software has appeared that displays sound files using two-dimensional maps. These maps are created by employing dimensionality reduction techniques to project the data into a two-dimensional latent space. This is analogous to creating embeddings to make 2D spaces using audio analysis to extract pertinent characteristics, from datasets and project their instances onto the space.

These 2D spaces, sometimes also called low-dimension spaces or sound similarity maps are generally created by first obtaining some form of high-level feature representation of the musical data. After that, based on data similarity dimensionality is lowered onto a 2D latent space. This has shown to be a successful method for streamlining massive collections of musical elements and enhancing user experience [4]. These dimensionality reduction techniques usually are MDS, PCA, t-SNE, or uMap. The sound similarity maps that are proposed often focus more on the representation and exploration of the musical blocks discussed above. Rare are the tools that support the creation of musical arrangements. Some popular tools that do so are [5], [6] or [7] which have the functionality to create patterns or arrangements of sounds that can be used in the context of music production. However, most tools including the ones mentioned above only focus on the representation of sounds using audio domain attributes. Only a few approaches utilizing symbolic data have been suggested, such as [8] or [9]. Furthermore, these tools have not been evaluated particularly in the context of a music production environment, creating a gap in understanding their effectiveness.

In this thesis, we build upon Rhythmspace, a graphical tool for organizing, visualizing, generating, and retrieving drum patterns based on rhythmic similarity [10] [8]. In Rhythmspace features are extracted from MIDI clips and are projected on 2d space for exploration and generation. We extend this Rhythmspace by creating a VST plugin that can be used in a DAW propagating its application in the music production environment. The Rhythmspace lacks evaluation within the music production space and so we evaluate it through a series of experiments.

Our main contributions are:

- (1) Using the introductory version of Rhythmspace to create a tool that can be used in a music production environment.
- (2) Using this tool to perform experiments with music producers for the evaluation of Rhythmspace to understand its usability and see if it is comparable to the traditional ways of drum creation. Following this we discuss the application and usability of

sound similarity maps in general.

The next sections in this thesis begin with delving into the current advancements in sound mapping and generation, with a particular focus on 2D maps and latent spaces. It then describes the approach adopted to develop the VST iteration of Rhythmspace and details the experiments designed to assess its efficacy within a music production setting. Following this, the results from these evaluations are thoroughly analyzed and discussed. The document ends with conclusions drawn from the research and a look into the potential aspects of future exploration.

Chapter 2

State of the Art

Browsing appropriate sounds and creating music within large collections of audio samples and MIDI data can be challenging for musicians and sound designers. Most digital audio workstations (DAW) provide list-based search options to organize media, as shown in Figure 1 and 2, while third-party software offers alternative browsing methods where sound files are projected within a two-dimensional map. This chapter will look at the most recent advancements in sound mapping and generation utilizing 2D maps and latent spaces.

Figure 1: Ableton Explorer View

Figure 2: Reaper Explorer View

2.0.1 Drum loop analysis, comparison, and generation

This section begins with a discussion of the analysis of drum loops and the feature extraction methods currently in use, with an emphasis on the symbolic domain. Then,

we outline methods that have been suggested for computing similarities among symbolic drum loops. We discuss various ways to generate drum loops at the conclusion of this section.

Feature extraction

The extraction of characteristics from audio data is a crucial step in any acoustical research and analysis. A suitable feature representation of the examined signals is necessary in order to fully comprehend these features. Various representation and extraction approaches for these features have been proposed and are still being worked on as part of the music information retrieval study. Several open-source libraries such as Essentia [11] or Librosa [12] are being proposed for audio and music analysis, as well as deep embeddings [13] for high-level representations. While many open-source resources are available for feature extraction using audio signals, only a few approaches utilizing symbolic music data have been suggested. Symbolic music data refers to a digital representation of musical information, capturing elements like pitch, duration, and dynamics, without containing actual audio waveforms. The symbolic format that we are using in this thesis project is called Musical Instrument Digital Interface (MIDI). MIDI is a standard to transmit and store music, originally designed for digital music synthesizers. MIDI does not carry any recorded sounds, rather it includes musical notes, timings, and pitch information, which the receiving device uses to play music from its own sound library [14]. Some object-oriented libraries for analyzing, generating, and evaluating symbolic music that has been very recently proposed are "Musicaiz" [15] and Rhythmttoolbox [8] for studying rhythms in the symbolic format. Music21 [16] is another popular library for the analysis of symbolic musical data. The ultimate objective of processing the audio or symbolic data for feature retrieval, irrespective variety of methods used, is to provide an acceptable numerical representation of the musical data. Because the backdrop of this work is around exploiting rhythmic features to improve the representation of drum loops and the creation of innovative drum patterns using these features, we will concentrate our efforts mostly on this area. Therefore, the next section delineates current research in drum loop analysis, comparison, and generation.

Similarity computation and Dimensionality reduction

Similarity Computation The core component of the thesis is to analyze symbolic drum loops to be able to compare them, evaluate and then generate them. For this, it is cardinal to be able to find similarities between the symbolic drum loops. While finding the similarities we want to limit our observations to the rhythm of patterns rather than tempo or meter, to simplify the analysis and typically these are static features fixed in the DAW [8]. We are also limiting our analysis of drum loops in the symbolic zone, due to our focus on symbolic drum loops.

Similarity computation has been an important aspect in the field of music information retrieval. It is the backbone of music recommendation systems and music classification systems. These computations can be classified into two categories, global similarity, and pattern similarity [17]. The term "global similarity" refers to computing similarities as a mixture of higher-level attributes characterizing elements. For example, the number of onsets, intensity of syncopation, or duration in musical data. On the other hand, pattern similarity works by specifying a distance metric that is calculated directly between two musical parts, pattern similarity seeks to characterize similarities between musical items.

The edit distance, which calculates how many insertions, deletions, or substitutions must be made to transform one symbolic rhythm into another, is an example of a pattern similarity metric [17]. Swap distance [18], hamming metric [19], Euclidean interval-vector distance [18]. Pattern Awareness Distance (PAD) [20] is another metric that belongs to the pattern similarity metric category.

Dimensionality reduction As discussed earlier, the combination of multiple sound similarity metrics and a vast array of descriptors, whether from the symbolic or audio domain, results in high-dimensional data. Consequently, effectively projecting this high-dimensional data into any given space poses significant challenges. Therefore, reducing the dimensionality of the data is imperative. There are a number of additional factors, such as the interpretability and identification of reduced feature sets or the removal of noisy and irrelevant features, as to why Dimen-

sionality Reduction techniques may be used to improve a model’s performance [21]. Additionally, when data is represented by high dimensional descriptors, it is more likely to be indistinguishable, which hurts similarity metrics. Feature selection or feature modification can be used in supervised or unsupervised learning to reduce dimensions. Common methods for dimensionality reduction, include multidimensional scaling (MDS) [22], which is a way of visualizing the similarity of points in a dataset, it accomplishes this by taking a matrix of dissimilarities or distances between data points and attempting to construct a point configuration in a lower-dimensional space that retains the relative distances as much as feasible. Other techniques commonly used are principal component analysis (PCA)s [23], and linear discriminant analysis (LDA) [24] which aims to find linear projections that maximize the separability between different classes. Whereas autoencoder neural networks [25], and t-SNE [26] or UMAP [27] offer nonlinear dimensionality reduction and are particularly effective for visualizing categorical data in lower-dimensional latent spaces.

Drum loops generation

While automatic music production systems have the potential to make music composition faster, simpler, and more fun, they can also enable new kinds of creativity or assist in inspiring new ideas in a music producer, acting as virtual partners [28]. Such systems frequently try to make music creation more accessible to beginner producers by automating certain difficult music production procedures. In this manner, music production might become more accessible to beginner producers, and will also help seasoned producers in their creative explorations, by giving them a starting point to build upon. This section focuses on reviewing the automatic generation of drum loops in the symbolic domain, as the context of this thesis is within the same.

While drum loop generation was rather rare in comparison to automatic melody or harmony generation systems, a small number of systems started being developed in the late 20th century. Langston’s Stochastic Binary Subdivision technique [29] is an early example of a drum loop creation system in 1989. The author provides six strategies for automatically generating short pieces in popular genres in this study.

One of the first systems designed to aid with music production was a system for automated synthesis of UK garage drum loops in the context of electronic music production[30]. "kin.rhythmicator" 3, a Max/MSP tool based on a set of global parameters like density, syncopation, and metrical feel is another tool that is proposed for creating drum loops [31].

Figure 3: kin.rhythmicator [30]

An alternate popular method for creating drum loops is to use evolutionary computation, particularly genetic algorithms, that are guided by natural selection. In recent work using a genetic algorithm for automatic drum loop generation, the authors use two-distance measures (the Hamming distance and directed-swap distance) to automatically create related patterns given an input pattern [32]. Furthermore, a system for generating interpolations between drum loops using conceptual blending, which is a technique for generating new conceptual spaces by blending two input spaces is also explored upon [33]. A different approach to crafting drum loops involves utilizing classic machine learning and music information retrieval (MIR) techniques. A drum loop creation system based on step-wise Markov probabilities was proposed [34]. In this system, each step location in the pattern is represented by a probability distribution. Users can dynamically adjust this distribution using three parameters: commonness/oddness (indicating the loop's typicality for a specific style), density (the number of hits), and syncopation. Similar to this method, [35] created a prototype rhythm variation generator based on the idea of strangeness, which may be used to produce variants on different loops. DrDrums [36] 4 produces loops in a user's

style by deriving a Markov model of style from a series of loops given by that user. With the emergence of deep learning architectures, the generation of drum loops using these techniques has gained significant attention and undergone extensive exploration. In a very recent example that uses deep learning, the authors created a real-time drum generation system capable of accompanying a human instrumentalist. The drum generation model is a transformer encoder trained to predict a short drum pattern given a reduced rhythmic representation [37].

Figure 4: DrDrums [36]

Because of their capacity to describe temporal correlations in data, recurrent and autoregressive deep learning architectures such as Recurrent Neural Networks (RNN), Long-Short Term Memory (LSTM), and Transformers are popular for all types of music generation. RNN-based sequence-to-sequence architecture to fill in drum loops based on a user-supplied kick drum pattern has been used before [38]. This model is a genre and kick drum pattern conditioned, providing two axes of control: input manipulation (creating the kick drum pattern) and parametric control via genre selection. An assistive drum pattern creation system for live performance employing a sequence-to-sequence architecture comprised of bidirectional LSTM encoder and decoder layers has also been created [39]. This system learns in real-time from human performance variations in response to human performance by pre-training on a huge dataset and then training further in real-time.

Subsequently, the Transformer architecture which has seen widespread popularity was applied to symbolic drum rhythm generation [40]. The authors' model can generate new rhythms from scratch and continue a user-written input rhythm. In

this work, a Transformer-XL model trained on the Magenta Groove MIDI Dataset is used for the tasks of sequence generation and continuation.

Variational autoencoder(VAE) [41] since their introduction has been prevalent for drum loop generation. GrooVAE [42] from Google’s Magenta team is one of the most well-known implementations of VAE, with several additional systems iterating on its design. RhythmVAE Max4Live plugin [43] 5 is such an extension, in which musicians can train a deep learning model by selecting target MIDI files from their own datasets, and then generate various rhythms with the model.

Figure 5: RhythmVAE [43]

A small number of approaches have also used Generative adversarial networks (GANs) [44], for drum loop generation. They were employed for drum loop creation in an intelligent drum machine app [45]. In this implementation, the training, and conditioning are used by the discriminator and generator networks to offer control over three parameters: genre, complexity, and loudness. The generator/discriminator architecture was enhanced with a third discriminator based on a genre classifier [46]. This architecture seeks to push innovation into the drum loop production system by training the generator to develop loops that do not suit any existing genre. Another very popular approach, although not for drum loops but rather for symbolic music generation and accompaniment was proposed by [47] in the museGAN project. This shows that GANs hold huge potential for generating symbolic data. However, despite the exploration wave, deep learning techniques have not proven to be better [48].

2.0.2 Music interfaces for music building block retrieval

In addition to the emergence of Music Information Retrieval (MIR) as a significant area of study, the last few years have seen a notable increase in the accessibility of music libraries. Researchers have focused their efforts on creating systems that can effectively view these libraries as a result. These systems referred to be content-based music retrieval interfaces, use MIR approaches to map musical data onto a 2D (or occasionally 3D) space in a way that tries to improve interaction with huge libraries of musical data [49]. In this section, many such interfaces are described. First, we discuss the interfaces produced by or in academic settings, and then commercially available products are discussed.

Research based approaches

In this subsection interfaces that are made for audio samples and audio loops, in general, are explored. After that, it focuses on drum sample retrieval systems, and towards the end drum loop retrieval interfaces are explored.

Several attempts have been made to visualize audio samples in a 2D space based on the timbral properties. For instance, In one of the early ideas for an audio loop navigation interface, the loops were used to extract harmonic, rhythmic, and timbral characteristics by computer-based techniques for analysis, synthesis, and perceptual scaling [50]. The Freesound Explorer [51] 6 is a more recent work that gives users the option to search for sounds using the Freesound API, display them based on their timbral similarity, and color-code each point in the visualization using the derived tristimulus descriptor. The Timbral Explorer [52] 7 shows how Audio Commons has also created a model to predict a variety of timbral classifiers, including hardness, depth, brightness, roughness, warmth, sharpness, boominess, and reverb.

Figure 6: Freesound Explorer [51]

Figure 7: Timbral Explorer [52]

Most time, metadata is also included in the feature representation, to display the samples in 3D space [53]. Another approach using a force-directed graphs projection was implemented as a web application for browsing a collection of audio loops from the freesound.com library [54]. In this method, to compare timbral and rhythmic content, MFCCs and beat spectrum are employed, and the loops are displayed on the 2D space as icons presenting a spectrogram. In subsequent attempts, researchers from Belmont University and Art+Log Inc. have developed a user-customizable surfing topology visualization and audio tagging interface called Vibrary [55]. It is a user-trainable neural network for audio tagging with user-specific and customizable tags

An early example of a drum sample retrieval interface was Drum Sample Explorer by [56], which blends a text-based interface with a graphical projection of a drum sample library based on the Self-Organising Map (SOM). An auditory filterbank-based representation of the drum samples serves as the feature vectors for SOM's similarity calculation. A more recent method for snare sample exploration was employed in the product AudioQuilt [7] 9, which projects the samples into a grid as opposed to a point cloud. Kernelized sorting is used to establish a 1-to-1 mapping between samples and the appropriate positions in the grid. In a contrasting approach, [4], an online application that incorporates a drum sample explorer, separates the instruments for the kick, snare, open hi-hat, and closed hi-hat into four distinct 2D maps. Instead of using an auditory filterbank-based representation, this projection is based on t-distributed stochastic neighbor embedding (t-SNE), but with a collection of timbral properties. [57] presents another method for visually organizing a drum sample library by using a timbral feature extraction approach.

While a lot of research has been done on content-based data retrieval interfaces for music composition, relatively little of it has been done on drum loops particularly. The first is the Rhythmspace, a generative 2D map interface suggested by [8] 8, which is built on a global-feature-based similarity model and can be used to explore and interpolate between a set of EDM drum loops. Another approach showcases a vast dataset of drum patterns and contrasts two distinct artificial neural network architectures that generate explorable latent spaces [58]. AudioStellar [5] 10, which, like the software previously described, displays the audio data as points in a two-dimensional space, serves as a proof of concept for contemporary 2D file browsers. Finally, Groove Explorer [9] 11 and Groove Explorer 2 [59] are two interfaces for the exploration of a library of symbolic drum loops, later being the most recent and updated version both being on a similarity-based visual representation of drum loops.

Figure 8: Rhythmspace [8]

Figure 9: AudioQuilt [7]

Figure 10: AudioStellar [5]

Figure 11: Groove Explorer [9]

Commercial software products

Several content-based retrieval interfaces for samples or loops have been developed in the context of music composition that have made their way into commercial

software. Applications like XO by XLN [6] 12 and Atlas by Algonaut [60] 13 expand on the concept of 2D file browsing by emphasizing giving the user the option to explore (mainly drum) one shot samples that may be utilized with the integrated drum sequencer to produce music more intuitively. Using the similar audio tagging method as proposed by [55], Sononym [61] adds further analysis to let users locate related sounds in their collection depending on any input sound source. COSMOS by Waves [62] 14 is one of the most recent software products for 2D sample browsing, combining several mapping layouts into one standalone application. It analyzes the audio, writes the metadata to an SQL database, and then uses different pre-trained models for classification and creates five different maps for the user to choose from. Besides the mapping view, the user has the option to find samples in a list-based search where files can be sorted by tags and timbral features. Another tool commercially available for symbolic drum loop mapping is Beat Map [63] 15 primarily targeted at EDM producers for sequencing a drum machine. Yet, the industry's focus on the difficulties of dealing with drum loops, as well as Reason's use of a 2D map, suggest that a content-based drum loop retrieval interface could be useful in practice.

2.0.3 Evaluation of lowD spaces as interfaces

Although there are many interactive spaces for music production and retrieval, user studies that evaluate them are relatively rare. Some studies that have been conducted on drum loop generation systems and interfaces, provide empirical evidence that they can be valuable tools for music production. This section outlines some of these studies.

A study was carried out by [4] to investigate the benefits of 2D visuals for drum sample retrieval interfaces. Within a system for drum kit configuration, the visualizations were applied and contrasted in a music composition task, in terms of both the exploration experience and the consequent output quality. Their research demonstrates that spatial visualizations improve the overall exploration experience and illustrate the potential of similarity-based arrangements for creative process as-

Figure 12: XO by XLN [6]

Figure 13: Atlas by Algonaut [60]

Figure 14: COSMOS [62]

Figure 15: BeatMap [63]

sistance. Another two related studies were carried out by [64] followed by an update to their system and its evaluation by [65]. For [64] the interface received excellent feedback from participants overall; 10 out of 11 participants said they would use it in a studio setting, and 9 said the interaction was intuitive and mentioned "It works as it should". It was described as "quick and practical", as well as "user-pleasant" in specific feedback. However, participants were hesitant to use the tool in a live performance owing to worries about its dependability. In the following study [65] the system varied from the previous in that it was operated by a touchscreen interface rather than a mouse. According to 10 participant interviews, the interface was intriguing, and the touch interface was quick and simple to use. The average rating for applicability in a production scenario was 4.7/5, while the overall grade was 4.7/5. Both studies show that assistive drum loop creation tools are beneficial as music production tools, allowing for faster and more intuitive drum loop composition.

The study carried out for the evaluation of DrDrums drum loop generation tool, [8] interviews two seasoned music producers who were asked to choose some original

drum patterns before having DrDrums create some drum patterns that fit their aesthetic. The participants said, "For musicians who are not so adept with rhythm it is fantastic," implying that this technology can make music creation simpler overall and especially for new producers. Finally, a study carried out by [66] five drum loop generation-related plugins from the Magenta Studio suite of Ableton Live plugins were evaluated in the survey. 'Continue', 'Generate', 'Interpolate', 'Drumify', and 'Groove' are plugins designed for creating and experimenting with drum loops. In a study of 89 users, 93% reported that the plugins increased their productivity, while 72% claimed they increased their creativity.

These evaluations employ various techniques for qualitative and quantitative evaluations. Some most common qualitative techniques include "Thematic Analysis" [67] or "Grounded Theory" [68]. Thematic analysis is a process that involves a systematic process of reading and re-reading the transcriptions, coding interesting features of the data, and then grouping these codes into broader themes that capture the core of the patterns. Grounded Theory involves the systematic identification of themes and the development of a theory that is 'grounded' in the data itself. It's an iterative process where data collection and analysis occur simultaneously. For quantitative evaluation techniques such as Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) [69], which is a statistical test used to analyze the difference between the means of more than two groups are used.

The most common pattern that can be observed from these evaluations is that while assistive drum loop generation tools generally receive positive feedback in the realm of music production, the assessments themselves often suffer from limitations. Specifically, many evaluations involve a limited number of participants and employ experiments characterized by ambiguous methodologies and questions. This lack of stringent and in-depth evaluation methodologies highlights a significant gap in the field. Realizing this, the aim of this thesis is to enhance the evaluation framework for these musical tools, ensuring a more comprehensive and insightful understanding of their impact and potential.

Chapter 3

Methodology: Rhythmspace Plugin Design & Development

This section delineates the systematic approach undertaken in this thesis project to both develop a VST based on Rhythmspace [8] and assess its efficacy in the context of the music production environment. The methodology is structured to provide a comprehensive understanding of the VST plugin's development process.

3.1 Design and Development of the Rhythmspace Plugin

The implementation of the Rhythmspace VST plugin that serves as a base for this thesis is based on the previous iterations of Rhythmspace employed in Puredata with its backend running in Python [8]. In this thesis project, the prototype is ported to C++ (JUICE framework) to create a VST allowing real-time MIDI and audio interaction inside a Digital Audio Workstation (DAW). This was required to assess Rhythmspace in the context of music production, as the technology transfer helps in running Rhythmspace as a VST in a DAW. It's essential to comprehend briefly how the Rhythmspace prototype works in Puredata and Python, in order to fully understand how it was developed as a VST plugin in JUICE.

3.1.1 Rhythmspace Puredata prototype

The general operation of the Rhythmspace prototype in Puredata as shown in Figure 17 revolves around a sound map that has points scattered representing MIDI files. These points are plotted using an appropriate similarity distance, which is calculated from the patterns themselves and corresponds to human sensations of similarity. As the user moves the cursor along this 2D space and goes around the scatter plot, drum patterns are generated by interpolation of different patterns. The pipeline is given in Figure 16 and it starts with the selection of a folder that contains MIDI drum patterns. The MIDI drum patterns that are acquired are split into 1-bar-long patterns. Using Rhythmtoolbox, all descriptors that are given in Table 1 are calculated and a normalized matrix is obtained where each column represents one feature and each row represents a drum pattern. Post this the Euclidean distance is extracted from each pattern in the collection. This data is used to generate a diagonal dissimilarity matrix that reports the distances between each pair. The multidimensional scaling method (MDS), which is programmed to extract a bi-dimensional solution for the dissimilarity matrix, processes this matrix at the end. The two coordinates to locate the various patterns in space are obtained in the final step, signifying a similarity-based organization.

Figure 16: Rhythmspace Puredata Block diagram [8]

Table 1: Rhythmtoolbox Descriptors

Descriptor	Explanation
noi	Number of instruments
polyDensity	Number of onsets
lowDensity	Number of onsets in the low freq band
midDensity	Number of onsets in the mid freq band
hiDensity	Number of onsets in the high freq band
lowness	Fraction of onsets in the low freq band
midness	Fraction of onsets in the mid freq band
hiness	Fraction of onsets in the high freq band
stepDensity	Fraction of steps with onsets
sync	Syncopation
lowSync	Syncopation of the low freq band
midSync	Syncopation of the mid freq band
hiSync	Syncopation of the high freq band
syness	Syncopation / density
lowSyness	Syncopation / density of the low freq band
midSyness	Syncopation / density of the mid freq band
hiSyness	Syncopation / density of the high freq band
balance	Monophonic balance
polyBalance	Polyphonic balance
evenness	Monophonic evenness
polyEvenness	Polyphonic evenness
polySync	Polyphonic syncopation

The Delaunay triangulation procedure is then applied to the coordinates to determine which sets of three patterns correspond to the triangles present in the bi-dimensional space. This triangulation is required for pattern interpolation which in turn generates MIDI patterns that are a combination of the three patterns present in that triangle. The coordinates obtained from MDS now can be projected on a

2D space and using Delaunay triangulation we obtain triangles. These triangles are the basis of the interpolation algorithm. In order to produce seamless transitions along the space, the algorithm weights the three surrounding patterns of any position in the rhythm space. A transition between three separate rhythms signals the formation of a new hybrid pattern with characteristics similar to the surrounding patterns. The interactive Graphical User Interface(GUI) is run in Puredata, but the backend processing of splitting MIDI files to generate hybrid patterns is done in Python and is run in the Puredata patch as an external.

Figure 17: Rhythmspace Puredata Prototype [8]

3.1.2 Rhythmspace VST plugin

The VST version of Rhythmspace 19 is made in the JUCE framework and employs a similar approach to operation. The pipeline is very similar to the Puredata prototype but the distribution of processes done in Python and natively in the JUCE framework is differently split as shown in Figure 18. For the VST, the operation starts similarly, the first step being to chop the MIDI files into 1-bar-long drum sequences. After that, using Rhythmtoolbox, the descriptors or features are extracted which are the same as the ones used in the Puredata version (Table 1). After feature extraction a normalized matrix is created and MDS is used to extract a bi-dimensional solution. This gives the two-point solution which, where each combination represents a MIDI

file and can be plotted. Using these points Delaunay triangulation is performed to get the triangles that are required for the pattern interpolation algorithm.

Figure 18: Rhythmspace VST plugin Flow Diagram

The process till now closely resembles the Puredata prototype. However, there are differences: the algorithms up to this point are executed in Python, and the pattern interpolation and interaction interface are developed in JUCE. Additionally, the results of each step are stored in a JSON format. This JSON file contains all the extracted features, MDS solutions, triangles from the triangulation process, and general information such as the name of the MIDI drum sequence, its genre, and folder location, etc. The pipeline, with its separation between the Python operation and the JUCE operation, can be seen in Figure 18. The JSON file serves as the foundation for the VST development in JUCE. Once loaded into the framework, all the data from this file is extracted and, as previously mentioned, fed into the pattern interpolation function written in JUCE. The pattern interpolation generates a 1-bar-long MIDI pattern as the output which is sent to the Digital Audio Workstation (DAW). While this method enhances the VST's speed, it necessitates the creation of a new JSON file whenever the dataset needs updating. However, this is a one-time process.

The VST version, depicted in Figure 19, shares the fundamental interaction GUI with the Puredata prototype, but it differs in the arrangement of individual elements

and the output format. Since the Rhythmspace plugin operates within a DAW, it must comply with the DAW's functioning rules, meaning it must be loaded as an instrument and output data supported by the DAW. Typically, this output is either an audio signal or a MIDI output. Given that we are dealing with MIDI format data, and the interpolation algorithm results in a 1-bar-long MIDI pattern, it was logical to output the result in MIDI format.

The interaction of the VST plugin mirrors the Puredata prototype, including a central scatter plot in the GUI. Below the scatter plot, there's a Piano roll component, along with knobs and buttons to accentuate various functions. These include a density knob to adjust the number of onsets in the MIDI pattern, a swing knob to add swing, and play and stop buttons to control the MIDI output to the DAW. Users can interact with the scatter plot using the mouse, moving the pointer to generate a hybrid pattern from a mixture of three MIDI patterns of the triangle the pointer is present. The output is most similar to the MIDI pattern closest to the pointer. Right-clicking on the scatter plot allows users to save a pattern temporarily while modifying it with the available knobs or recording it in the DAW's MIDI channel. The VST plugin then generates a 1-bar-long MIDI output, which users can hear by loading an instrument of their choice, such as a drum machine or custom drum rack. The video demo of the VST plugin and its GitHub repository code can be accessed via the links in Appendix B.1.

Figure 19: Rhythmspace VST

Chapter 4

Experiments Evaluating Rhythmspace

The evaluation of spaces like Rhythmspace within the music production environment has been notably sparse. To address this gap, we designed experiments centered on the use of Rhythmspace for music creation. Our primary objective was to assess the usefulness of the Rhythmspace plugin in the music production process and compare it with traditional ways of drum creation. To this end, we devised two main experiments: a composition experiment and a subsequent listening test.

In the composition experiment, participants were tasked with crafting drum sequences that would complement pre-composed audio tracks provided to them. The independent variable in this context was the method employed to create these drum sequences, while the dependent variable pertained to the musicality of the resulting sequences. This experiment aimed to discern whether the music produced with the assistance of Rhythmspace was comparable to that produced without its aid. Building on the results of the composition experiment, we then designed a listening test. This test sought to understand whether drum sequences crafted using Rhythmspace resonated as well with listeners as those created without the plugin.

The experimental process was bifurcated into two distinct phases. The initial phase engaged participants with a background in music production. They were given

the challenge of creating drum sequences for pre-composed tracks spanning three genres: House, Lofi, and Hip-hop, all through the Rhythmspace plugin. These genres were chosen as they form the base of a wide variety of genres presently popular in electronic music. The subsequent phase, the listening test, involved participants from a broad spectrum of musical backgrounds. These participants were tasked with ranking the drum sequences generated during the first phase. The following sections delve deeper into the intricacies of these experiments.

4.1 Experiment 1: Evaluating Rhythmspace in Music Production

In this experiment participants with a diverse set of music production expertise were asked to create drum sequences.

4.1.1 Preparation

For the experiment, a diverse set of audio tracks was crafted that encompass three genres: House, Hip-Hop, and Lo-Fi. Using Ableton Live, a popular Digital Audio Workstation, we produced two distinct audio tracks for each genre to provide variety to the participants. The audio tracks were original compositions and all tracks were set in a 4/4 metric, a common time signature in electronic music. The tempos were chosen based on the range of what’s commonly associated with each genre: 124 bpm for House, 110 bpm for Lo-Fi, and 135 bpm for Hip-Hop. The links to all 6 tracks are given in Appendix A.1.2. The pre-composition was done beforehand so that the participants focus just on drum sequence creation and not on the other musicality of the audio tracks. The dataset for generating the Rhythmspace consisted of 71 MIDI files, which when chopped into 1-bar-long drum sequences equated to roughly 140 loops. To ensure a uniform experimental setting, we established a controlled environment within which the participants used Ableton Live for the experiment. For precise audio monitoring, we employed the Audio-Technica ATH M50x headphones.

The participants selected for this experiment were music producers falling under

various expertise levels: Beginner, Intermediate, and Advanced.

1. Participants having 1 to 2 years of music production experience are categorized as "Beginner".
2. Participants having 3 to 4 years of music production experience are categorized as "Intermediate".
3. Participants having 5 + years of music production are categorized as "Advanced".

Participants needed to have prior hands-on experience with Ableton, ensuring they were familiar with the DAW's functionalities. Furthermore, they should have incorporated MIDI patterns regularly in their music productions. Lastly, an understanding of drum sequencers was required, as this knowledge would be pivotal in navigating the experiment's tasks.

4.1.2 Procedure

The procedure of the experiment starts by collecting the following personal data from the participants:

- **Full Name**
- **Email**
- **Age**
- **Gender**
- **Relation with Music:** To gauge their musical background and involvement, participants selected one of the options on a 6-point scale, starting with 1 year of experience to point 6 being 5+ years of experience

After this, in the experiment, participants were tasked with crafting drum sequences tailored to provided pre-composed musical accompaniments. The drum sequence

should be such that the finished output can be used as a seed for making a complete song. The participants were asked to create the drum sequences in three ways:

1. Utilize the provided MIDI clips present in the “library explorer view”.
2. Utilize the Rhythmspace
3. Use your preferred workflow to create the sequence.

Participants were presented with three distinct methods for creating drum sequences. The first method provided them with pre-composed MIDI patterns, which they accessed through the default library explorer view in Ableton Live—a list-based explorer. For the second method, participants utilized the Rhythmspace plugin. The third method was open-ended, granting participants the freedom to craft drum sequences as they saw fit, whether by using their own patterns, samples, drum racks, or other tools. The participants were however provided a basic set of drum essentials from Ableton Live, which includes drum machines like Roland TR-808, TR-909, and TR-707 among others, one-shot drum samples, and pre-composed drum loop MIDI files [70].

Upon commencing the experiment, participants were guided through a structured procedure, the script of which is given in the first Appendix A.1.1. Initially, they were exposed to six different pre-composed tracks, specifically curated for this experiment. The links to these tracks can also be found in Appendix A.1.2. From this pool consisting tracks from three genres: House, Hip-Hop, and Lo-Fi, they were asked to choose two tracks that resonated with them the most. Their task was then to craft three drum sequences for each of the selected tracks using the three methods previously outlined. Furthermore, while participants could edit the drum patterns in Methods 1 and 3, Method 2 was centered around exploring the Rhythmspace, where the editing capability is inherently built into the plugin.

To ensure focus and efficiency, a time constraint was imposed: participants were allotted 15 minutes per track, culminating in a total experiment duration of 30

minutes. Following the creation of six drum sequences, once the hands-on portion of the experiment concluded, participants were presented with a comprehensive survey to gather their overall impressions and feedback. The survey was made using Google Forms. This was complemented by a short interview, allowing for a deeper dive into their experiences, challenges, and insights garnered throughout the process. The specific questions asked in the interviews are given in the following section.

The entire script that was provided to the participants can be found in Appendix A.1.1 along with the link to survey A.1.2

4.1.3 Evaluation: Rhythmspace in the context of Music production.

Quantitative Evaluation As described before, this experiment involves interaction with Rhythmspace in which participants use the VST plugin and create drum sequences using the three methods. Participants are asked to provide information about their musical experience at the start of the experiment in terms of years of producing music. This data is used to categorize the participants into three categories: Beginners, Intermediates, and Advanced.

This categorization is useful to understand the scale of the responses across different levels and whether the experience of Rhythmspace changes between these levels. After the categorization, four box plots are plotted, one for overall combined responses for all participants and the other three for the responses of each category of participants. The box plots are plotted to identify the distribution, central tendency, and variability of the responses within and across each category. Specifically, the box plots will provide insights into the median, quartiles, and potential outliers in the data. This visual representation will allow for a clear comparison of how beginners, intermediates, and advanced users interact with and perceive Rhythmspace.

Furthermore, this analysis will help in identifying any significant differences or trends in the responses of participants based on their musical experience. For instance, if beginners tend to struggle more with a particular approach in Rhythmspace com-

pared to advanced users. Similarly, if all categories of participants show a consistent pattern of responses, it might suggest that the specific method in Rhythmspace is universally intuitive or challenging, regardless of the user's musical background.

Qualitative Evaluation The experiment also incorporates a subjective interview with participants about their experience with Rhythmspace. The questions asked in the interview were:

1. **Most Useful Feature:** What feature of the Rhythmspace plugin do you find most useful in your music production process?
2. **Preferred Approach:** Do you prefer using the Rhythmspace plugin's interpolation approach to generate MIDI patterns or a traditional drum sequencer? Please explain your choice.
3. **New Affordances:** What new possibilities or affordances has the Rhythmspace plugin introduced in your music production process?
4. **Additional Features:** Are there any additional features or improvements you would like to see in the Rhythmspace plugin?

Given the subjective nature of these responses, a qualitative evaluation is necessary. To facilitate this, the audio recordings of the interviews are transcribed into text using the open-source "Whisper" model from OpenAI [71]. These transcriptions are then analyzed to extract key points that appear most often, such as the comments on the User Interface or on specific functionality of the plugin, which are subsequently presented in the results section of the thesis. The interviews lasted on average around 5 minutes and were done one-on-one just after the participants finished all the tasks.

For the analysis of these transcriptions, thematic analysis [67] was employed. The thematic analysis involves a systematic process of reading and re-reading the transcriptions, coding interesting features of the data, and then grouping these codes into broader themes that capture the core of the patterns. The codes or patterns

that were anticipated from the experiment were themes such as the value of the "scatter plot" feature and the benefits of "real-time" capabilities, among others. The insights from this analysis, including these expected themes and potentially more, are presented in the results section of the thesis.

4.1.4 Results: Rhythmspace in the context of Music production.

The primary objective of this experiment was to evaluate the Rhythmspace plugin in the context of music production, especially when juxtaposed against traditional methods and participants' preferred workflows. The results presented herein are derived from both the drum sequences crafted by the participants and their feedback obtained through the post-experiment survey and interview.

The experiment was conducted between a diverse group of 10 participants with different music production expertise spanning between beginner, Intermediate, and Advanced levels. A brief overview of the participants' demographics is as follows:

1. **Age:** The participants' ages ranged from 26 to 38, the most frequent age group being 26 years old. All of the participants identified as male and the distribution of different ages is given in Figure 20a
2. **Musical Experience:** Participants' musical experience was counted on a 6-point scale. The distribution included five beginners (two with 1 year and three with 2 years of experience), three intermediates (spanning 3 to 4 years), and two advanced participants with over 5 years of experience. Figure 20b visually illustrates this distribution.

(a) Age Distribution

(b) Musical Experience Distribution

Figure 20: Experiment 1 Distributions

Survey Results

As outlined in the methodology, following the drum sequence creation, participants completed a post-experiment survey. This survey comprised fourteen questions, for clarity in visualization, abbreviated versions of these questions are displayed on the box plots. The complete questions can be found in Appendix A.1.2. Responses were collected using a Likert scale and subsequently visualized through box plots. These plots offer a comprehensive view of participants' feedback, both overall and segmented by the three expertise levels. The boxplots can be seen in Figures 21, 22, 23, and 24.

Figure 21: All Participants

Figure 22: Beginner Participants

1. **Overall Feedback, Figure 21:** The feedback from all 10 participants predominantly shows that the Interquartile Range (IQR) — which captures the middle 50% of responses — leans towards the positive end of the scale (above 4). This suggests a generally positive perception of Rhythmspace across all participants, indicating that music producers, irrespective of their expertise level, appreciate the tool's value.

2. **Beginner Participants' Feedback, Figure 22:** The unanimous rating of 6 from 5 beginner participants for "understanding of the plugin's functionality" indicates a clear and high appreciation of the plugin's clarity. In contrast, the "degree of surprise from the output" and "Novelty of MIDI patterns" have a wider range of responses, from 2 to 5, suggesting varied reactions to the unexpected elements of the output.

Figure 23: Intermediate Participants

Figure 24: Advanced Participants

3. **Intermediate Participants' Feedback, Figure 23:** The three intermediate participants gave a consistent rating of 4 for "frequency of surprise" suggests that participants were regularly surprised by Rhythmspace's drum sequences. The "understanding of features in Rhythmspace" and its interface show varied responses, indicating different experiences or interpretations. Overall, the experience with Rhythmspace is positive, with a median rating of 5, and no ratings exceeding this value, emphasizing a shared positive perception among the intermediate group.
4. **Advanced Participants' Feedback, Figure 24:** The two advanced participants provided feedback that is generally positive, with all ratings above the neutral point of 3. Both participants found the "frequency of surprise" to be moderate, rating it at 3. Their overall experience with Rhythmspace was notably positive, with a rating of 5. The "novelty of patterns" was rated positively at 4. However, the "uniqueness" of Rhythmspace saw a broader range of opinions, with ratings spanning from 3 to 6 and a median of 4.5.

In Summary, the feedback from participants across different expertise levels underscores the positive reception of Rhythmspace. While there were variations in specific aspects, the overarching sentiment is one of positiveness with respect to the value derived from the tool.

Thematic Analysis of Interviews

The primary objective of this study was to understand the perceived utility and potential improvements of the Rhythmspace plugin from the perspective of music producers. A total of 10 participants were interviewed, and their responses were subjected to a thematic analysis. The results are presented below, organized by the main themes identified.

1. Most Useful Feature of the Rhythmspace Plugin

Visual Organization: A significant number of participants (60%) highlighted the visual aspect of the plugin as its most salient feature. The scatter plot rep-

resentation, which provides a visual organization of patterns, was particularly appreciated for its ease of navigation and quick overview.

Interpolation: 50% of the participants found the ability to interpolate between patterns by moving around the scatter plot to be a unique and beneficial feature of the plugin.

Density Control: 30% of participants mentioned density control as a standout feature, noting its capability to modify patterns and generate related ones.

2. Preference: Rhythmspace vs. Traditional Drum Sequencer Use Case

Dependency: A majority of participants (70%) felt that the choice between the Rhythmspace plugin and a traditional drum sequencer was not binary. Instead, the decision depended on the specific use case, for instance, in case they want to start something from scratch Rhythmspace can be a good starting point, but if they have something in mind that they want to recreate exactly they would directly work on creating it using their preferred methods.

Exploratory vs. Premeditated Production: 40% of the participants viewed the Rhythmspace plugin as more suitable for exploratory work, especially when seeking inspiration. In contrast, if they had a specific rhythm in mind, they might lean towards a traditional sequencer.

3. New Affordances Introduced by the Rhythmspace Plugin

Quick Inspiration: 50% of the participants felt that the plugin served as a tool for rapid inspiration, especially useful during creative blocks.

Real-time Interaction: 40% of the participants appreciated the real-time interaction feature, especially the ability to adjust parameters like density on the fly.

Genre Interpolation: 30% of participants found the ability to interpolate between different genres of drum patterns to be a novel and intriguing feature.

4. Suggested Features or Improvements for the Rhythmspace Plugin

Drag and Drop Functionality: This was the most common suggestion, with

60% of participants expressing a desire for a drag-and-drop feature to move generated patterns directly into a track.

Multiple Cursors: 10% of participants felt that having multiple cursors or points in the scatter plot would enhance the plugin’s functionality. This way they can select multiple points on the Rhythmspace and can create a trajectory that goes in between these points, creating a morph of many drum patterns.

Improved UI Indications: 20% of participants felt that the user interface could benefit from clearer indications, such as better zooming functionality or more explicit genre indications.

The Rhythmspace plugin was seen as a useful instrument for music producers, particularly for those seeking instant inspiration or a fresh method for creating drum patterns. The visual aspect of the plugin, combined with the interpolation feature, was especially appreciated. However, it was also clear that the plugin would not replace traditional drum sequencers but would instead complement them. Suggestions for improvements were mainly focused on enhancing the user experience by adding functionality such as zooming or dragging the MIDI pattern directly on the MIDI track in a DAW.

4.2 Experiment 2: Ranking Drum Sequences

In the follow-up to the initial experiment, a secondary study was curated to understand if the Rhythmspace plugin outperforms or is on par with the other approaches that music producers often use in their music creations. We wanted to test if drum sequences produced with Rhythmspace are not consistently ranked worse than the other methods.

4.2.1 Preparation

From the results of the original experiment consisting of 60 audio tracks, 12 audio tracks were handpicked and exported with the drum sequences and the musical accompaniment, representing the work of three distinct producers. These tracks

spanned three genres: House, Lofi, and Hiphop, with a distribution of 6 tracks from House and 3 each from Lofi and Hiphop.

To facilitate the ranking process, a survey was constructed using Psytoolkit [72] [73]. Participants were presented with the 12 tracks in sets of three. Notably, each set was composed of the three methods employed in the first experiment, ensuring that every audio piece had a drum sequence paired with its pre-composed musical accompaniment from each method. For example, if a House music track was picked, the three variations of the drum sequences (method 1, Rhythmspace, and method 3) were included. The ranking mechanism was interactive, allowing participants to drag and arrange options based on their preferences. Leveraging Psytoolkit’s random function, both the order of the three audios within each set and the sequence of genre-based questions were randomized, ensuring unbiased responses. Participants were instructed to use headphones for an optimal listening experience. The survey was hosted on PsyToolkit’s server, with participants accessing it via a shared link. The entire script that was provided to the participants can be found in Appendix A.2.1 along with the link to the survey A.2.2.

4.2.2 Procedure

As previously noted, the survey’s primary task was to rank the audio tracks sourced from Experiment 1. This study sought to identify preferences among participants from various musical backgrounds, concentrating on their preferred drum sequences obtained from the three methodologies established in Experiment 1. Participants evaluated both the musicality between the drum sequence and its accompanying music, as well as the overall musicality of each track.

In the introduction, a link to all the genres was provided so that participants become familiar with what they will be listening to. Before delving into the main task, participants were prompted to provide some personal details to help contextualize the results and ensure a diverse range of feedback. The collected information included:

- Full Name

- Email
- Age
- Relation with Music: To gauge their musical background and involvement, participants selected one of the following options:
 1. I listen to music daily but don't have any other relation.
 2. I play an instrument and have some knowledge.
 3. I am a musician, producer, music creator, or similar.

This demographic data not only offered insights into the participants' backgrounds but also helped in understanding the diverse perspectives they brought to the experiment.

In the main activity, participants were presented with 12 short music tracks, grouped in sets of three. After each set, they were tasked with two primary questions:

1. How would you rank the piece in terms of its general musical quality?
2. How would you assess the drum track's harmony with the other musical elements?

An example of the structure of a typical question is given below: Listen to the tracks labeled as Track A, Track B, and Track C. Post listening, drag, and arrange the tracks based on your preference, considering the following questions. 1. How would you rank the pieces in terms of their general musical quality? 2. How would you rank the relation of the drum track with the rest of the elements of the piece?

The participants can then drag and arrange the sequence according to their preferences. Four sets of these questions were presented in the survey. At the end of the survey, participants had an option to voluntarily leave any feedback they had about the survey.

4.2.3 Evaluating Participant’s Drum Sequences

The primary goal of the second experiment was to determine participant preferences for drum sequences created utilizing the three methods from Experiment 1. Because the data was organized (rankings of three methods over numerous tracks and genres), the study required a method that could manage comparisons across several groups. Other than plotting the aggregate of the number of votes each method received by ranks, the most appropriate statistical approach for this purpose was determined to be ANOVA (Analysis of Variance).

Based on the Relation with Music information provided by the participants at the start of the survey, participants were categorized into three distinct groups:

1. Listeners: Individuals who listen to music daily but don’t have any other relation.
2. Hobbyists: Those who play an instrument and have some foundational knowledge.
3. Professionals: Individuals who identify as musicians, producers, music creators, or similar.

This categorization was crucial as it allowed for a nuanced analysis, considering the potential differences in preferences and perceptions across varying levels of musical engagement.

Before conducting the ANOVA, the dataset underwent a cleaning process. This ensured that any discrepancies, missing values, outliers, or incomplete surveys were addressed, leading to a more robust analysis. The rankings were rearranged to maintain a consistent order: Method 1, Rhythmspace (RS), and Method 3. This consistency was crucial for a standardized comparison across all tracks and participants.

The data was also bifurcated into two, one part had all the rankings given for the overall musicality variable. This data corresponds to the first question in which

we asked participants to rank the pieces in terms of their general musical quality. The other part had all the rankings given for the drum relation variable, which corresponds to the second question in the survey where we asked participants to rank the method with respect to the relation of drum sequence with its musical accompaniment.

ANOVA was employed for each part of the data, to compare the mean rankings of the three methods across the selected tracks. The primary aim was to determine if drum sequences made using Rhythmspace are not consistently ranked worse than the other methods. Additionally, we wanted to examine if there were statistically significant differences in the preferences for the drum sequences produced by the three methods. The independent variable in this analysis was the 'Method' with three levels (Method 1, RS, Method 3), while the dependent variable was the 'Ranking' given by participants. Additionally, the categorization of participants was considered as a between-subjects factor to explore if preferences varied based on their musical background. To delve deeper into the influence of musical background on preferences, separate ANOVAs or interaction effects were analyzed for listeners, hobbyists, and professionals. This helped in understanding if, for instance, professionals had a different preference pattern compared to casual listeners. If the p-value from the ANOVA was less than 0.05, a post hoc Tukey test was conducted. This test helped identify where the meaningful differences lay among the three methods, providing a better understanding of participants' preferences.

4.2.4 Results: Ranking Drum Sequences

In this section, we present the findings from the second experiment, focusing on the ranking of drum sequences produced using the three methods: Method 1, Rhythmspace (RS), and Method 3. The goal of this experiment was to understand how Rhythmspace is performing in comparison to the other methods.

The experiment was conducted between a diverse group of participants with different music production expertise spanning between Listener, Hobbyist, and Professional levels. A brief overview of the participants' demographics is as follows:

1. **Age:** The participants' ages ranged from 22 to 62, the most frequent age group being 26 years old. The distribution of different ages is given in Figure 25a
2. **Musical Experience:** Participants' musical experience was counted on the basis of their input of the expertise at the start of the experiment. The distribution included nine listeners, six hobbyists, and 7 professionals. Figure 25b visually illustrates this distribution.

(a) Age Distribution

(b) Musical Experience Distribution

Figure 25: Experiment 2 Distributions

In the following sections, the results are analyzed based on the rankings provided by participants. In the first section, we present the average ranking of all three methods dissected by considering the participants' musical backgrounds, categorized

as Listeners, Hobbyists, and Professionals. In the later section, we present the results of the ANOVA statistical analysis.

Average Rankings

This section elucidates the collective preferences for the drum sequences produced using the three distinct methods: Method 1, Rhythmspace (RS), and Method 3. To visually represent these preferences, we've employed a series of bar graphs. On the x-axis of each graph, the three methods are delineated. The y-axis, meanwhile, quantifies the number of votes each method received. For clarity, each method is represented by three bars:

1. The first bar showcases the number of votes a method received for being ranked first.
2. The second bar indicates the votes for a method being ranked second.
3. The third bar displays the votes for a method being ranked third.

The initial chart provides an overarching view, illustrating the overall ranking preferences across all participants. Subsequent charts delve deeper, segmenting the rankings based on participants' musical backgrounds: Listeners, Hobbyists, and Professionals. This bifurcation offers insights into how musical experience and engagement might influence preferences.

1. Overall Rankings 26: As can be observed from the chart Method 1 is ranked the best, Rhythmspace the second best and Method 3 the last.
2. Ranking by Listeners 27: In the case of Listener's preferences, the distribution is more even, although the Rhythmspace is still ranked the second best in this category
3. Rankings by Hobbyists 28: In the case of hobbyists, the ranking is more lopsided but follows the distribution of overall ranking, Method 1 ranked the best, Rhythmspace ranked the second best and Method 3 the last.

Figure 26: Overall Ranking

Figure 27: Ranking by Listeners

- Ranking by Professionals 29: For Professionals, Method 1 and Rhythmspace received an equal number of votes, with Method 1 being ranked first and Rhythmspace second. Once again, Method 3 received the lowest ranking in this category.

From the drum sequence rankings, clear patterns surfaced across groups. Overall data 26 showed Method 1 leading, with Rhythmspace second and Method 3 last. Listeners' preferences 27 were more balanced, but Rhythmspace still ranked second. Hobbyists 28 followed this trend. Notably, professionals 29 equally favored Method

Figure 28: Rankings by Hobbyists

Figure 29: Ranking by Professionals

1 and Rhythmspace, while Method 3 remained the least preferred across all groups. The consistent ranking of Rhythmspace as the second best underscores the potential and efficacy of Rhythmspace in the realm of music production, especially given its strong performance among professionals.

ANOVA analysis

Using ANOVA, we assessed if there were statistically significant differences in the rankings of the three methods. The results of the ANOVA are presented, detailing the F-statistic, degrees of freedom, and the p-value. If the p-value was found to be less than 0.05, indicating a statistically significant difference, a post hoc Tukey test was conducted to identify where these differences lay among the three methods. Since the data was bifurcated into two one for drum relations rankings and the other for general musicality rankings, two separate ANOVAs were conducted for each.

ANOVA for Drum Relation Rankings The descriptive analysis for this part of data where we are testing the performance of Rhythmspace in the context of drum relation with its musical accompaniment is given in the table 2.

Method	Number of Observation	Mean	Standard Deviation
Method 1	88	1.98	0.86
Rhythmspace	88	1.88	0.73
Method 3	88	2.11	0.80

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics for Drum Relation

A one-way between-subjects ANOVA was conducted to compare the effect of the method of production on ranking in Method 1, Rhythmspace, and Method 3 conditions. There was not a significant effect of the method of production on ranking at the $p < .05$ level for the three conditions [$F(2, 85) = 1.55, p = 0.214$]. Given the non-significant result of the ANOVA, post hoc tests such as Tukey's HSD were not conducted, as they would not provide meaningful differentiation between the groups.

In simpler terms, In the case of when the ranking is considered for the relation of drum sequence with the musical accompaniment, the method of production did not have a significant effect on the ranking of the music sequences. All three methods (Method 1, Rhythmspace, and Method 3) produced similar rankings, and no method stood out as being superior or inferior based on the data collected.

ANOVA for General Musicality Rankings The descriptive analysis for this part of the data where we are testing the performance of Rhythmspace in the context of the overall musicality of the audio tracks is given in the table 3.

Method	Number of Observation	Mean	Standard Deviation
Method 1	88	1.80	0.81
Rhythmspace	88	2.08	0.69
Method 3	88	2.13	0.88

Table 3: Descriptive Statistics for Overall Musicality of the track

A one-way between-subjects ANOVA was conducted to compare the effect of the method of production on ranking in Method 1, Rhythmspace, and Method 3 conditions. There was a significant effect of the method of production on ranking at the $p < .05$ level for the three conditions [$F(2, 85) = 4.30, p = 0.015$]

Post hoc comparisons using the Tukey HSD test indicated the following:

1. The mean ranking for Method 1 was significantly different from Method 3, with a mean difference of -0.330, 95% CI [-0.617, -0.042], $p = 0.020$.
2. The mean ranking for Method 1 differed marginally from Rhythmspace, with a mean difference of -0.284, 95% CI [-0.571, 0.003], $p = 0.053$.
3. There was no significant difference in the mean rankings between Rhythmspace and Method 3, with a mean difference of -0.045, 95% CI [-0.333, 0.242], $p = 0.926$.

In other words, the method of production had a significant effect on the ranking of the music sequences. Specifically, Method 1 produced significantly different rankings from method 3, while the difference between Method 1 and Rhythmspace was marginally significant. No significant difference in rankings was observed between Rhythmspace and Method 3. This is probably because the drum sequences produced in method 3 are more abstract and don't follow a specific trend, as method 3

was an open-ended approach. Participants were free to create the drum sequence as they liked and therefore the musicality of these patterns can prove to be subjective, hinting towards the less significant difference.

When assessing the relation of drum sequences with musical accompaniment, the production method showed no significant effect on rankings; all methods yielded similar results. However, for general musicality, the production method was influential. Specifically, Method 1 and Method 3 had notably different rankings, with Method 1 and Rhythmspace showing a borderline difference. In essence, while the drum sequence's relation to accompaniment was consistent across methods, general musicality rankings varied. If we focus on the Rhythmspace result, Rhythmspace's drum sequences align similarly with musical accompaniment as the other methods. In terms of general musicality, it was almost distinct from Method 1 but was comparable to Method 3. This suggests that the drum sequences created by the Rhythmspace plugin when considered with their musical accompaniment were ranked very closely to method 3 and method 1. Therefore, it can be presumed that the Rhythmspace performed in comparable to the other methods, even to method 3 which gave full freedom to the participants to create drum sequences, proving its utility in the context of music production.

The Jupyter Notebooks containing the code for the Experiment analysis can be accessed via its GitHub repository code via, the links in Appendix B.1.

Chapter 5

Conclusions

In this chapter, we draw conclusions and suggest future research directions based on the development and evaluation of the Rhythmspace VST.

5.1 Discussion

The primary goal of this thesis was to evaluate Rhythmspace in the context of music production to understand its usability and see if it is comparable to the traditional ways of drum creation. To recap, Rhythmspace offers a two-dimensional space for exploring and generating drum patterns in symbolic MIDI format. Rhythmspace in its current version is tailored for musical genres that fall under the umbrella of electronic music. To this end, it was essential to port Rhythmspace into a tool that can be accessed in a Digital Audio Workstation (DAW), the environment that most electronic music producers use to create their music. The Rhythmspace prototype therefore was ported to a VST plugin using the JUCE(C++) framework and Python. After developing the tool, we designed a series of experiments to assess its usefulness and the quality of drum sequences it produces within a music production environment.

In the initial composition experiment, 10 participants of varied music production expertise crafted drum sequences using three distinct methods for two tracks, cho-

sen from a set of six spanning three genres: House, Hip-Hop, and Lofi. The methods were method 1: using already curated MIDI clips, using Rhythmpace, and method 3 where they had the freedom to employ whatever style they preferred to create drum sequences. They were then asked to fill up a survey and were asked questions about their experience with the Rhythmpace. This experiment highlighted the Rhythmpace plugin's utility for music producers, especially those seeking fresh inspiration. Its user-friendly interface and the high-quality drum sequences it generated were met with moderate to high positive feedback. However, through the interviews, it was also evident that the plugin would not replace traditional drum sequencers but would instead complement them. This is understandable because if the music producer already knows the exact drum sequence they want to create, they would directly go and create it using whatever method they prefer, and the exploratory aspect of Rhythmpace will not prove to be a significant value addition.

In the following experiment, a listening test was designed. In the listening test, the results of experiment 1, meaning the drum sequences created by participants paired with the musical accompaniment were picked and presented to participants. A total of 12 tracks were picked out that consisted of three genres: House music(6 tracks), Hip-Hop (3 tracks) and Lofi (3 tracks). The participants were asked to rank their preferences for these 12 tracks presented to them in a set of 3 tracks corresponding to each method from experiment 1. The listening test was evaluated using the statistical analysis tool ANOVA and by calculating the aggregated ranking each method received.

In evaluating the drum sequences using ANOVA, two distinct aspects were considered: the relation of the drum sequence with the musical accompaniment and the general musicality of the sequences. When focusing on the relation of the drum sequence with the musical accompaniment, the method of production did not significantly influence the rankings. All three methods - Method1, Rhythmpace, and Method3 - yielded comparable rankings, with no single method emerging as distinctly superior or inferior. Conversely, when assessing general musicality, the method of production played a pivotal role in the rankings. Specifically, there was

a notable difference between the rankings produced by Method 1 and Method 3. Meanwhile, the difference in rankings between Method 1 and Rhythmspace was on the cusp of significance. Rhythmspace and Method 3, however, did not exhibit any significant difference in their rankings. This suggests Rhythmspace’s drum sequences aligned similarly with musical accompaniment as the other methods. In terms of general musicality, it was almost distinct from Method 1 but was comparable to Method 3.

In a more straightforward evaluation, where we considered aggregate rankings, the results were more definitive. The number of votes each method got for each rank shows a clear indication that Rhythmspace is consistently ranked second best, which solidifies the hypothesis that we wanted to test, which is that the drum sequences produced with Rhythmspace are not consistently ranked worse than the other methods.

In conclusion, this thesis presented a VST version of Rhythmspace compatible with any DAW. The VST was proven to be a tool that adds value to the music producers in their process of drum creation, and the results of it are at least on par with other methods that the music producers might employ.

5.2 Future Works

The current implementation of the Rhythmspace VST plugin is bifurcated into two distinct parts. Initially, a structured JSON file is created, containing details of the MIDI files, such as metadata and computed features, and is the compact version of the Rhythmspace database. This file, crafted in Python, subsequently forms the foundation for the VST developed in JUCE. While this division between Python and JUCE ensures a more efficient VST plugin, it introduces constraints. Specifically, any modifications to the database, such as adding or removing MIDI files, necessitate the recreation of the JSON file. This confines Rhythmspace’s utility to its existing database. If users wish to integrate their MIDI files, they must manually generate this JSON file using the provided Python script—a task that might be daunting

or inconvenient for many. Therefore, to enhance user experience and flexibility, future iterations of the plugin should incorporate a feature allowing users to directly select and process MIDI files within the plugin itself, automatically generating the requisite JSON file. This enhancement would render the plugin more user-friendly and adaptable to diverse databases.

Additionally, feedback from participants who utilized Rhythmspace also offered valuable insights for future enhancements of the VST plugin. Several constructive suggestions emerged, including the introduction of a drag-and-drop feature to transfer drum sequences directly to a DAW's MIDI track. Another proposed enhancement is the ability to use multiple points within Rhythmspace, facilitating the morphing and creation of drum sequences across genres. Additionally, a straightforward zoom functionality could significantly improve user interaction. Implementing these suggestions could greatly amplify the tool's usability and overall user experience with Rhythmspace.

The experimental results validate our initial hypothesis: Rhythmspace performs comparably to other methods that music producers utilize for drum sequence creation and that the Rhythmspace adds value to their music creation process. However, certain outcomes from the listening test remain ambiguous. Conducting the test with a larger sample could yield more definitive results, potentially resolving the existing ambiguities.

List of Figures

1	Ableton Explorer View	4
2	Reaper Explorer View	4
3	kin.rhythmicator [30]	8
4	DrDrums [36]	9
5	RhythmVAE [43]	10
6	Freesound Explorer [51]	12
7	Timbral Explorer [52]	12
8	Rhythmspace [8]	13
9	AudioQuilt [7]	13
10	AudioStellar [5]	13
11	Groove Explorer [9]	13
12	XO by XLN [6]	15
13	Atlas by Algonaut [60]	15
14	COSMOS [62]	15
15	BeatMap [63]	15
16	Rhythmspace Puredata Block diagram [8]	18
17	Rhythmspace Puredata Prototype [8]	20
18	Rhythmspace VST plugin Flow Diagram	21
19	Rhythmspace VST	23
20	Experiment 1 Distributions	31
21	All Participants	32
22	Beginner Participants	32
23	Intermediate Participants	33
24	Advanced Participants	33

25	Experiment 2 Distributions	41
26	Overall Ranking	43
27	Ranking by Listeners	43
28	Rankings by Hobbyists	44
29	Ranking by Professionals	44

List of Tables

1	Rhythmtoolbox Descriptors	19
2	Descriptive Statistics for Drum Relation	45
3	Descriptive Statistics for Overall Musicality of the track	46

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Appendix A

First Appendix

A.1 Experiment 1

A.1.1 Script

Welcome to our experiment, where we are assessing a tool designed to generate drum MIDI patterns. This brief guide will help you understand the experiment and your role in it.

Our primary goal is as follows: We want you to create engaging drum patterns that complement a pre-composed harmonic and melodic track such that your drum sequence:

1. Span a duration of 4 bars
2. Can serve as a starting point for composing a full song.

You will use these three methods to create these drum sequences:

1. Utilize the provided MIDI clips present in the “library explorer view”.
2. Utilize the Rhythmspace.

3. Use your preferred workflow to create the sequence.

We will provide drum one-shot drum samples that you can use to create drum racks. You are also welcome to use your own drum samples to create the drum racks, and this time will not be counted as part of the experiment.

Here's the procedure you'll follow:

1. Listen to 6 different pre-composed tracks prepared for the experiment.
2. Select 2 tracks you prefer from the pool of 6.
3. For each track create a drum sequence using the three methods mentioned above.
4. You will have a time limit of 15 minutes per track, resulting in a total duration of 30 minutes.
5. After creating the drum sequences, you will complete a survey regarding the outcome.
6. After the experiment: You will be asked to complete a survey, and we will conduct a short interview with you.

Please note, that Methods 1 and 2 will use the same dataset, while Method 3 allows for an open-ended approach using your own workflow. You can make edits to the drum patterns in Methods 1 and 3, Method 2 involves exploring the rhythm space and editing is inbuilt into the rhythm space.

We appreciate your participation and look forward to seeing the creative drum sequences you produce!

A.1.2 Links: Experiment 1

1. Survey Link

2. Interview Transcripts
3. Pre composed Audios

A.2 Experiment 2

A.2.1 Script

About this study Welcome to this listening test, and thank you for participating!
In this experiment, you will be listening to pieces in three music genres:

1. House
2. Hip-Hop
3. Lofi

Please listen to the three genres before proceeding.

The experiment presents 12 short music tracks in groups of 3 and asks you to rate them by their musicality. After listening to the tracks you will answer two questions:

1. How would you rate the piece in terms of its general musical quality?
2. How would you rate the relation of the drum track with the rest of the elements of the piece?

Please use headphones while doing the survey.

Take your time; it should take you more or less 10 minutes to complete the test.

A.2.2 Links: Experiment 2

1. Survey
2. Survey Audios

Appendix B

Second Appendix

B.1 Code Links

1. JUCE GitHub Repository: GitHub Repository containing the JUCE (C++) code of the VST plugin
2. Experiment analysis: GitHub Repository containing all the Jupyter Notebooks for analysis of experiment data
3. Rhythmspace VST Demo